

Edible Electronic Components Made from Recycled Food Waste

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A procedure is developed for producing basic electronic components utilizing materials sourced from discarded orange, grapefruit, lemon, apple, banana, potato, and carrot peels. Initially, these materials undergo dehydration, followed by a meticulous pulverization process to obtain fine powder. Natural adhesives like water, honey, sugar, starch, and gelatin are employed to interconnect the materials. Formed substrates are characterized using Scanning Electron Microscopy, Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy, and an optical profilometer. Furthermore, the relative permittivity of the materials is determined. Three distinct types of substrates, derived from the aforementioned peels, are crafted in varying dimensions. Substrates measuring 4 cm × 2.5 cm host interdigital capacitive sensors, whereas larger 6 cm × 3.5 cm substrates accommodate inductor-capacitor (LC) sensors. Each of the six samples undergoes individual dry testing, while LC sensors are additionally tested with the post-application of artificial saliva and mouthwash liquids. The sensor's characterization involves measurement of impedance and phase angle for all samples. Capacitance is additionally measured for capacitors, and inductance for LC circuits. These assessments are carried out within the frequency range spanning from 1 MHz to 400 MHz. The objective is the development of fully functional electronic components, derived from discarded edible items, fostering sustainable practices, and finding applications in biomedicine.

24%, and 35%, respectively.^[1] Namely, ≈83% of food in food supply chain gets wasted, what is very alarming.^[2] Therefore, the increasing amount of food waste generated every year has led to the exploration of alternative ways to utilize this waste. The multifaceted and complex issue of food waste integration with sustainable production has been discussed in various studies.^[2,3] One such innovative and sustainable approach is the development of electronic components from food waste creating in consumption stage, particularly from peels of edible raw food collecting each day in restaurants, homes, and food industry.^[4] The use of such food waste as a source material for electronic components, is anyhow might be very promising in reducing the environmental burden and impact of electronic waste, providing a sustainable solution for waste management. Efficient utilization of waste, besides important in solving environmental problems, also will have a positive impact on the economic problems of society, by increasing resources and creating new

1. Introduction

Globally, it is estimated that in the food supply chain loss of food in production, postharvest, and consumption stages are ≈24%,

sources of income. The transformation of waste materials into high-end applications is a promising area of research encompassing environmental and economic aspects, leading to advancements in materials science, chemistry, and engineering. The need for raw materials can be reduced which leads to natural resources conservation and lowering the environmental impact of resource extraction. Moreover, the volume of waste sent to incinerators is reduced. By transforming food waste into high-end applications, it is possible to create new markets and revenue streams, which can stimulate economic growth and foster the creation of sustainable solutions (a circular economy model). Finally, given the finite nature of many resources, a shift toward sustainable practices, including food waste transformation to the high-end electronic components, is essential for the long-term viability. There also initiatives and efforts in valorizing waste materials like wool in electronics.^[5,6]

In the last decade, there has been an accelerated development of Green Electronics, and in particular, a significant number of research groups have published very notable works in the field of edible and biodegradable electronics.^[7] Edible electronics are a growing field of technology, developing devices from edible

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Table 1. Overview of recent edible components realizations.

Reference, year	Used material	Fabricated component and application
[8], 2023	Riboflavin and quercetin on activated carbon	Rechargeable battery for power supply (48 μ A @ 0.65 V) is made by immobilizing riboflavin and quercetin on activated carbon. The anode is made of riboflavin while the cathode is made from quercetin. The encapsulation of the electrodes is done with beeswax.
[11], 2022	Edible oil-derived activated carbon	Edible biocompatible capacitors and supercapacitors based on molecular growth of hydrocarbons. The fabrication process includes burning the mustard oil and activation of Zinc chloride, followed by use of tubular furnace with controlled temperature to 900 °C.
[12], 2018	Biomass-derived carbon induced by cellular respiration in yeast	Supercapacitor based on warm water activated yeast with banana peels that were carbonized in muffle furnace at 900 °C for 1 h.
[13], 2022	An isomalt (form of a sugar)	Capacitors, planar inductors, helical inductors, and inductors with an edible core. The basic material was isomalt pellets initially heated to 200 °C, followed by dip coating.
[14], 2018	Genetically engineered <i>E. coli</i> bacteria	Hybrid sensors for bleeding detection with inclusion of genetically engineered bacteria.
[15], 2023	Carrageenan, polyvinyl alcohol, and apple pomace-based	A temperature sensor, based on apple pomace and sucrose, for use in oral cavity.
[16], 2021	Honey as an electrolyte gate dielectric	Edible transistors with humidity responsivity for potential moisture control of dried or dehydrated food.

materials,^[8] whereas manufacturing methods, components, and possible applications of edible electronics are described in.^[9,10] Very inspiring recently published works are presented in **Table 1**.

In addition to the fabrication of electronic components with procedures that include genetical engineering and carbon activation, the creation of electronic components and circuits is also possible from food waste (the discard of edible items of raw food). The design and development of food waste-inspired electrochemical platforms for various applications was described in.^[17] Skin of potatoes has shown some new ideas and possibilities when harvesting and storing or packaging potatoes.^[18] A study deals with hybrid aerogels obtained from banana peels and waste paper for efficient oil absorption.^[19] Synthesis of silicon dioxide and silicon from sugar cane residues was reported.^[20] The properties of bacterial cellulose film obtained on a substrate from sweet potato waste were studied in.^[21] It has also been shown that carbon obtained from biomass can be used in supercapacitors,^[22] and in addition, the synthesis of metal particles from natural resources and food waste and their application has been described.^[23]

This paper presents the process of manufacturing edible sensor structures on substrates made of food scraps, i.e., fruits and vegetables. The process of making the substrate included the dehydration and pulverization of seven biomaterial types (banana, orange, apple, grapefruit, lemon, potato, and carrot – peels). Obtained substrates were characterized in terms of composition (Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy), determination of dielectric constant, as well as microstructural properties (Scanning Electron Microscopy and Optical Profilometer). In further steps, a successful realization of interdigital capacitors and inductor-capacitor (LC) resonant circuits has been achieved. In addition, the influence of Paradont mouthwash and artificial saliva on the functionality and sensitivity of the LC sensor was investigated. Based on the results, it can be concluded that sensor structures placed on substrates obtained from food residues could be used to measure certain parameters in the oral cavity. The main advantage of edible sensors when compared to the implantable or ingestible is enhanced safety and reduced risk

upon ingestion. On the other hand, the advantages of our work when reported to relevant works from the literature are elimination of need for genetical engineering, carbon activation, and dip coating or application of high-temperature furnaces. In addition to that, the commercial dielectric substrates, such FR-4 (flame retardant), includes more complicated fabrication procedures with etching, photoengraving, lamination, drilling, solder slating, and silk screening. Consequently, the proposed processing of food waste is more time-efficient, and it requires less energy.

2. Methods and Materials

2.1. Procedure for the Fabrication of Edible Substrates and Conductive Electrodes Deposition

Three different edible substrates were prepared with the goal of utilizing them in printed edible electrical components, such as interdigitated capacitors and resonant circuits. Substrates were made from powders of: 1) Lemon, Orange, and Grapefruits and it would be denoted here and further as LOG, 2) Orange, Grapefruits, Apple, and Banana that would be denoted here and further as OGAB, and 3) Carrot peels, Potato peels, and Lemon, denoted here and further as CPL. The proportion of waste materials in the composite samples was chosen based on the required hardness of the substrate and its uniformity. Equivalent quantities of primary components (to achieve a total of ≈ 9 – 10 g, which was sufficient to create a single substrate suitable for use in our mouth) were selected, except for samples containing banana peel, where a larger amount of banana was added. This was done considering that the fiber content of the banana additionally contributed as a binding agent in the sample, ensuring reliability even at elevated temperatures.

For OGAB substrate 4 g of banana, 2 g of apple, 2 g of orange, and 2 g of grapefruit powders were used. The production process involved heating a small amount of distilled water together with the mentioned ingredients, to obtain a homogeneous, rubbery structure. Then, a substrate of the desired dimensions was formed by placing the mixture in previously made molds with

Figure 1. a) Steps in fabrication of IDE capacitors and LC circuits made on substrates from raw food waste, b) mask designs for the conductive electrodes deposition in the process of forming IDE capacitor (4 cm × 2.5 cm) and c) LC circuit (6 cm × 3.5 cm).

dimensions of 6 cm × 3.5 cm and 4 cm × 2.5 cm. They were left to dry at room temperature for several hours, until the mixture hardened, and then light compression was applied to preserve the correct shape.

For CPL substrate, the equivalent amount of powered ingredients consisting of 3 g of carrot, 3 g of potato, and 3 g of lemon, which were interconnected using gelatin, was used. The procedure involved heating the gelatin to the melting temperature and then combining it with the mentioned ingredients. The resulting homogeneous mixture was then poured into a previously made mold with dimensions of 6 cm × 3.5 cm and 4 cm × 2.5 cm. After a few minutes of drying at room temperature, the samples were removed from the mold and placed to dry on a flat surface to maintain a smooth structure. Light compression was also performed evenly over the entire sample during drying to avoid curling of the edges.

The LOG substrate consists of 3 g of grapefruit peel, 3 g of orange peel, and 3 g of lemon peel. They were also connected to each other with gelatin, with the difference that the mentioned ingredients and gelatin were heated simultaneously at a low temperature. After melting the gelatin and obtaining a homogeneous mixture, it was poured onto a flat surface, and then, after a few minutes of cooling, shapes with dimensions of 6 cm × 3.5 cm and 4 cm × 2.5 cm were cut out. The drying procedure was carried out in the same way as for the previous sample.

For composite samples manufacturing, 3 g of gelatin was used, as an effective binding agent, along with ≈15 milliliters of water to enable complete hydration and dissolution of the gelatin granules. The adhesive qualities of gelatin were most effectively demonstrated with this ratio, ensuring the appropriate assembly and functionality of the proposed components. The hydrogen bonds present in gelatin had a role in the creation of a network, which resulted in the desired texture and consistency of structures formed from powders derived from waste materials. An essential benefit of utilizing gelatin was that its melting point is very close to the average human body temperature, and it allows gelatin to be easily digested in the concept of edible electronics. Furthermore, gelatin possesses excellent nutritional value and biodegradable properties.

A convenient approach for the manufacturing of the edible electronic components, based on the raw food waste, could be the planar structure, as shown in **Figure 1a**. For example, capacitors with interdigital electrodes (IDE) or planar LC circuits (composed of capacitor and inductor). Such structures found a wide range of possible applications and offer benefits in terms of lower cost with smaller use of conductive materials for creation of electrodes. In this work, the creation of conductive electrodes on the edible substrates includes deposition of golden leaves on the top of the substrate. The patterns for interdigital capacitor and planar LC resonator were cut using the cutter plotter as a mask for deposition of edible gold on the top of the substrates. The substrate is slightly moistened with water before the sheet of edible gold was placed over the mask. Applying gold to the substrate involves tapping and pressing on the surface, to obtain the desired structure. The process was repeated until a compact, continuous conductive line was created, followed by the removal of the unused material. Created masks and later used for the deposition of conductive material for the creation of IDE capacitor and planar LC resonator are shown in **Figure 1b,c**, respectively. The dimensions of the baseline samples used for characterization are 4 cm × 2.5 cm for capacitor, and 6 cm × 3.5 cm for the LC circuit. Toward the further miniaturization of components, capacitors with smaller dimensions were also manufactured. Fabrication outcomes and results of the performed electrical characterization are available in subsections 3.5 and 3.6.

The presented dimensions were selected to be very similar to the average biscuit size, ensuring safe placement in the oral cavity during the measurements. Further analysis and circuit size optimizations of capacitor and LC circuit were planned as it is reasonable to expect that with careful layout and component sizing was possible to improve the device performance. The goal of this study was to present proof of the concept transformation of food waste into useful electrical components, with potential to improve the overall possibilities of sensing in the oral cavity by using edible materials. The size of the fabricated sensors was comparable to the size of commercially available sensing solutions, such PLANMECA intraoral sensor (39.7 mm × 25.1 mm and 44.1 mm × 30.4 mm),^[24] DIGISENS Intraoral Dental X-ray

Sensor (33 mm × 25 mm)^[25] or Vatech EzSensor HD Intraoral Sensor (31.3 mm × 42.9 mm × 4.80 mm),^[26] etc.

Main advantages of the proposed method edible material synthesis were simplicity, time efficiency, there was no waste of material as the complete amount of the input material was totally used was transformed into usable substrate. When compared to the edible materials synthesis based on carbon activation, the advantages were lower cost, elimination of impact on the pH value, and pore blockage, which were the characteristic of activated carbon.^[27]

2.2. Characterization Methods

A detailed characterization study of investigated substrates was performed. First, optical profilometry (Optical Profilometer model HRM300, Huvitz) was used to evaluate the surface of the substrates of interest. 3D and 2D images were acquired, with two separate magnification factors: ×25 and ×100. A scanning electron microscope (TM3030, Hitachi High Technologies) was used to take high resolution images of the substrates. As the substrates exhibit low conductivity, the images were taken at different magnifications, depending on the clarity of the substrate. Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy was applied as an analytical technique for the elemental analysis of substrates.

Mechanical properties of sample were analyzed with two tests: 1) three-point bending test to determine the maximum breaking force of the edible substrates, and 2) nanoindentation. The maximum breaking force was determined in accordance with ISO 178 procedure for 3-point tests (flexure properties) of rigid and semi-rigid plastics. This system for tensile, compression, and flexure testing (34SC-2) belongs to the 3400 series of INSTRON, Norwood, MA, USA.

The microprobe-based testing of mechanical properties was performed with Nano Indenter G200 system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, California, USA). Motivation for using nanoindentation was to gain insights into the fundamental behavior of the materials under investigation, particularly in distinguishing between plastic and elastic deformations. Nanoindentation was performed with the following parameters: active force of 100 mN, one dwelling per location, peak hold time 1 s, dwelling time 15 s, Poisson's coefficient 0.1, with total 25 measurements (5 × 5 matrix with 250 μm spacing over *x* and *y* axis). The load versus displacement curves are later depicted in Figure 3. The obtained results indicate pronounced plasticity and non-uniformity across all samples. The Young's modulus for LOG and OGAB samples exhibited similarity, measuring at 0.509 (± 0.421) and 0.482 (± 0.425) GPa, respectively, while the CPL sample demonstrated a higher Young's modulus of 0.972 (± 0.799) GPa. Similarly, the hardness results followed a parallel trend, with LOG and OGAB samples showing comparable values of 0.005 (± 0.005) and 0.007 (± 0.007) GPa, and CPL displaying greater hardness at 0.014 (± 0.015) GPa. When interpreting these findings, a large standard deviation implies that the samples necessitate enhanced preparation procedures. Refinement in polishing and homogenization techniques was imperative to enable finer measurements of Young's modulus and hardness. However, no additional alterations to the samples were considered necessary for the current

study. Instead, nanoindentation outcomes were leveraged to discern the plastic or elastic characteristics inherent in the materials under scrutiny.

Additionally, dielectric properties of fabricated edible substrates were determined by measurement of the relative permittivity. The measurement setup for the determination of the dielectric constant was composed of the manufactured parallel plate capacitor (two parallel copper electrodes at a fixed distance 1 mm and 0.5 mm, depending on the substrate thickness). Using electrical impedance measurement device (HIOKI, Chemical Impedance analyzer), the capacitance was measured on 4 frequencies (0.1, 1, 10, and 100 kHz). First, the capacitance (C_0) was measured with air as the dielectric between the plates. That was followed by impedance measurements with added edible substrates. Measurements were repeated three times for each substrate type. Mean values and standard deviations were used for the stability analysis and comparison between LOG, OGAB, and CPL.

Capacitance and impedance (modulus and phase angle) of the fabricated capacitors were determined. Inductance and impedance measurements were performed for the LC circuit. Moreover, to the measurement of the dry LC samples, the sensing properties were also studied. Artificial saliva (Apoteke Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia) in a volume of 0.1 ml was applied to the LC surface and the measurement procedure was repeated after a few minutes. Moreover, 0.1 ml of Paradont, a mouthwash liquid, was also applied to the LC surface, and measurements were repeated. The reason for studying the behavior of the LC circuits in environments based on the artificial saliva and a mouthwash liquid, was to determine suitability for applications in oral cavity, and for the analysis of the oral liquids. These tests would reveal the stability of the manufactured substrates in aqueous environments and will provide insights about sensitivity in terms of response to different liquids that are typical for the oral cavity. Electrical impedance measurement device (HIOKI IM7585, Japan) was applied for measurements in $N = 201$ points with the frequency range from 1 MHz to 400 MHz. The selected values for detailed analysis and comparison were selected to be at four frequencies: 100, 200, 300, and 400 MHz.

3. Experimental Results and Analysis

3.1. Optical, Microstructural, and Elemental Characterization of LOG, OGAB, and CPL Substrates

The pieces of fabricated substrates of LOG, OGAB and CPL substrates are depicted in Figure 2.

The full set of obtained 2D and 3D figures, by means of optical profilometry, is available as the Supplementary material of this manuscript (Figures S1–S3, Supporting Information). The full set of obtained SEM images is also available as the Supplementary material of this manuscript (Figures S4–S6, Supporting Information). SEM imaging was done to determine the consistency of the elemental structure of the materials used.

High uniformity can be seen on the CPL edible substrate on magnification of ×1.5k. Contrary to that, chunks which come from grapefruit and oranges, as zirconium (Zr) is localized on

Figure 2. Fabricated substrates from food waste: a) LOG, b) OGAB, and c) CPL.

them, can be seen under magnification $\times 1.2k$ on LOG substrate. It is important to note the chunk size is ≈ 0.5 mm. Finally, the edible substrate denoted as OGAB, had small chunks, ≈ 0.05 mm in size. They are most likely remnants of bananas as potassium is found here in higher concentrations.

Furthermore, optical profilometry was done with the goal of qualitatively showing the coarseness/smoothness of the substrates. EDX spectroscopy analysis of LOG substrate showed that the normalized concentration of the elements such as carbon, zirconium, and oxygen was 59.01, 22.24, and 18.75 wt.%, respectively. In the case of OGAB substrate, the presence of oxygen, carbon, calcium and potassium was registered with the normalized concentrations of 51.28, 34.41, 12.77, and 1.54 wt.%, respectively.

3.2. The Determination of Mechanical Properties of LOG, OGAB, and CPL Substrates

Photos of the test equipment (Instron 34SC-2), with the detailed presentation of the sample with the fixture and the process of substrate bending before break, are available in Figure S7 (Supporting Information). The obtained values for the maximum breaking force of LOG, OGAB, and CPL substrates are 2.2307, 4.4143, and 3.3511 N, respectively. The corresponding flexure stress values of LOG, OGAB, and CPL substrates are 44.05, 10.90, and 8.85 MPa, respectively. The graphical comparisons of obtained results, as well as the test equipment are shown in Figure 3. Figure 3 also depicts the results of nanoindentation results for all three substrate types. Results for OGAB substrate (thickness 1.039 mm) are shown in Figure 3c, LOG substrate (thickness 0.741 mm) in Figure 3d, and for CPL substrate (thickness 1.056 mm) in Figure 3e. The maximum indentation depth in the OGAB and LOG curves is comparable, slightly exceeding 10 μm , whereas the CPL sample exhibited a maximum depth of ≈ 8 μm . All load versus displacement curves suggest a characteristic plastic behavior across all materials, closely resembling that of PCB (Printed Circuit Board) material, commonly employed in electronic circuit production.^[28]

The robustness observed in the mechanical tests suggests that these substrates can withstand various mechanical stresses, such as bending and stretching, which are relevant in the context of wearable and ingestible electronics.

3.3. The Determination of Relative Permittivity of LOG, OGAB, and CPL Substrates

The obtained (mean \pm standard deviation) values for the relative permittivity of LOG, OGAB, and CPL substrates at frequencies of 0.1, 1, 10, and 100 kHz are summarized in Figure 4. The materials showed relatively independent frequency characteristics with the range of relative permittivity 1–2, which is like the Polytetrafluoroethylene and electroactive polymers, but higher than spin-coated sugarin.^[13]

3.4. Fabricated Components Based on LOG, OGAB, and CPL Substrates

The next step was realization of IDE capacitors and LC circuits that are based on the fabricated substrates, as shown in Figure 5. The integral components of fabrication process (edible substrate, mask design for conductive electrode deposition and the sheet of edible gold) are also shown in Figure 5a.

3.5. Electrical Characterization of the Manufactured IDE Capacitors

Experimental setup for the electrical characterization of manufactured IDE capacitors and LC circuits is shown in Figure S8 (Supporting Information), while the results are shown in Figure 6a–c for CPL (Sample #1), Figure 6d–f for LOG (Sample #2), and Figure 6g–i for OGAB substrate (Sample #3). The capacitance characteristic of the interdigital capacitor designed on the CPL type of substrate is predominantly linear, with a mean value of 3.404 pF. The range of capacitance values ranges from a minimum of 3.110 pF to a maximum of 4.596 pF. The values of impedance and resistance are decreasing with increasing frequency. Impedance ranges from 24.70 Ω to 40.40 k Ω , and resistance from 8.79 Ω to 8.09 k Ω . The values of the phase angle range from -74.01° to -88.22° , which indicates the capacitive nature of the realized component. The LOG-based IDE capacitor is also characterized by a linear capacitance characteristic, the values vary from 2.992 to 5.367 pF. Impedance and resistance are also decreasing as frequency increases. Impedance and resistance values are from 92.30 Ω to 34.00 k Ω and from 2.49 Ω to 11.70 k Ω , respectively. The values of the phase angle are in the range from -82.73° to -89.45° , which confirms the expected capacitive nature of this component. The OGAB-based type of IDE capacitor also has a linear capacitance characteristic, with a mean value of 2.447 pF. The range of capacitance values ranges from a minimum of 2.270 pF to a maximum of 3.520 pF. The impedance and resistance characteristics are decreasing as frequency is increasing, as in the case of the previous two capacitors. Impedance values are in the range from 151.10 Ω to 55.10 k Ω , while the resistance is from 0.24 Ω to 12.05 k Ω . The phase angle values are also $\approx -90^\circ$, with a range from -87.41° to -90.46° .

Table 2 shows the comparison of the capacitance values for all three components at frequencies 100, 200, 300 and 400 MHz. From the presented results, it can be concluded that the IDE capacitors with CPL and LOG substrate have similar characteristics, which can be explained by the similarity of the substrate on which

Figure 3. a) The breaking forces, b) flexure stress for analyzed three samples, c) nanoindentation analysis of OGAB, d) nanoindentation analysis of LOG, and e) nanoindentation analysis of CPL.

they were designed. The smaller values of capacitance for OGAB-based capacitor can be explained due to the lower dielectric constant of that substrate, based on adhesive used in its preparation.

The capacitance of the interdigital capacitor is calculated according to the Equation (1):

$$C = (\epsilon_r + 1) l [(N - 3) A_1 + A_2] \text{ (pF)} \quad (1)$$

where represents the dielectric constant of the substrate, l [m] the finger length of the interdigital capacitor, N the number of fingers, A_1 [pF/m] and A_2 [pF/m] approximations, which are calculated based on the ratio of the height of the substrate material and the width of the conductive lines. Comparison of the calculated values with the measured values revealed that there is no deviation greater than 0.3 pF.

Figure 4. Relative permittivity plots of LOG, OGAB, and CPL substrates on a specific frequency.

Figure 5. a) The integral components of fabrication process; pictures of the fabricated: b) CPL-based IDE capacitor (Sample #1), c) LOG-based IDE capacitor (Sample #2), d) OGAB-based IDE capacitor (Sample #3), e) CPL-based LC circuit (Sample #4), f) LOG-based LC circuit (Sample #5), and g) OGAB-based LC circuit (Sample #6).

Capacitor on CPL substrate - Sample #1

Capacitor on LOG substrate - Sample #2

Capacitor on OGAB substrate - Sample #3

Figure 6. Measurement results for Sample #1: a) impedance; b) phase angle; c) capacitance, Sample #2: d) impedance; e) phase angle; f) capacitance and Sample #3: g) impedance; h) phase angle; i) capacitance.

Table 2. The capacitance of all three capacitors at specific frequencies.

Frequency	Capacitance		
	CPL-based capacitor	LOG-based capacitor	OGAB-based capacitor
100 MHz	3.144 pF	3.141 pF	2.295 pF
200 MHz	3.281 pF	3.275 pF	2.345 pF
300 MHz	3.611 pF	3.625 pF	2.442 pF
400 MHz	4.405 pF	4.318 pF	2.629 pF

3.6. Electrical Characterization of the Manufactured LC Circuits

The characteristics of the LC sensor designed on the CPL substrate (Sample #4) are shown in Figure 7a–f for LOG (Sample #5), and Figure 7g–i for OGAB substrate (Sample #6). These characteristics include impedance, phase angle and inductance. In the case of CPL-based substrate, the phase crosses zero at a frequency of 164 MHz, and that at the same frequency the impedance has a peak, i.e., the highest value of 370 Ω. That frequency is called the resonant frequency, and it is detected by the device when the frequency of the sensor itself coincides with the frequency of the transmitter. The inductance has values of the order of nH, with a

LC circuit on CPL substrate - Sample #4

LC circuit on LOG substrate - Sample #5

LC circuit on OGAB substrate - Sample #6

Figure 7. Measurement results for Sample #4: a) impedance; b) phase angle; c) inductance, Sample #5: d) impedance; e) phase angle; f) inductance and Sample #6: g) impedance; h) phase angle; i) inductance.

maximum value of 217.78 nH. The values of the phase angle vary in the range from -52.40° to 60.96° . The self-resonant frequency (SRF) of the LC sensor designed on the LOG substrate (Sample #5) is found to be 168 MHz, while the impedance reaches a maximum of 370 Ω at that frequency. The inductance of the sensor has values of the order of nH, up to 187 nH, and the phase angle varies in the range from -55.60° to 51.97° . Obtained resonant frequency of the dry OGAB-based sample was 146 MHz, with the impedance value of 277 Ω . The inductance also ranges in nH, with the maximum up to 178 nH. The values of the phase angle vary in the range from -48.24° to 55.93° .

The next step involved applying artificial saliva to the surface of the sensor to observe its physical and chemical reactions to this liquid. Measurements were taken 5 min after applying 0.1 ml of artificial saliva. Then, 0.1 ml of Paradont, a mouthwash, was added to the surface of the sensor, and measurements were taken again within 5 min. As the dielectric constant of saliva and Paradont is higher than the dielectric constant of the test sample itself, the increase in the concentration of these liquids inside the sensor resulted in an increase in the capacitance of the interdigital capacitor. As a result, the resonant frequency decreased, which is expected considering that

Figure 8. Comparison graph of the change in resonant frequency.

these two parameters are inversely proportional, according to the Equation (2):

$$f_0 = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{LC}} \quad (2)$$

Also, there was a drop in impedance, which results from the fact that a wet sample has a higher permittivity than a dry one, and therefore its total capacitance is reduced.

The resonant frequency of the CPL-based dry sample is 166 MHz, while for the sample with saliva is 145 MHz and for the sample with Paradont 141 MHz. A drop in the resonant frequency for LOG-based substrate was 146 MHz after the application of saliva and 140 MHz after the application of mouthwash liquid-Paradont. Capacitance changes due to the addition of liquid also caused changes in the resonant frequency of the LC circuit based on the OGAB substrate, which dropped from the initial 146 MHz of the dry sample to 139 MHz of the sample with artificial saliva, and then to 133 MHz in the sample with Paradont.

It is noted that all samples have similar characteristics of all three parameters, with small deviations in the values. All components react the same when artificial saliva and Paradont are added to their surface – there is a decrease in impedance and inductance, and the phase crossing point with zero occurs at a lower frequency. Figure 8 shows a graph comparing the behavior of the resonant frequency of all three samples.

The resonant frequency decreases in all three samples after the application of the liquid, which is a consequence of the change in the dielectric constant of the samples. Sample #4 has a frequency drop of 19 MHz after application of artificial saliva, Sample #5 a drop of 22 MHz, and Sample #6 a drop of 7 MHz. After the addition of Paradont, the resonant frequency of Sample #4, Sample #5, and Sample #6 decreased by 4, 6, and 6 MHz, respectively. Therefore, Sample #5 – LC sensor made on a LOG substrate, proved to be the sample with the highest sensitivity, given that for the same amount of liquid applied to the sample surface, it had the largest step change in resonance frequency.

3.7. Fabricated Sensors with Smaller Dimensions and Applications of Food-Based Electronic Components

Our first intention has been to turn food products waste into useful electronic components and that “green” or environmentally friendly dimension is the high value of this work. The proposed electronics components have various implications for practical applications, which encompass: four major fields: 1) biodegradable electronics, 2) food packaging, 3) educational tools, and 4) biomedicine. For example, the utilization of consumable electronic substrates aligns with the burgeoning demand for eco-friendly and degradable electronic components. This can be particularly pertinent in mitigating electronic waste, particularly in disposable and short-lifecycle applications. The incorporation of food-based or food waste-based circuits into food packaging materials could offer a novel means of monitoring food freshness or safety. Additionally, food-based electronic circuits can function as captivating educational tools, particularly in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) disciplines. They provide a hands-on approach for students to comprehend the fundamentals of electronics, simultaneously introducing the concept of sustainability and responsibility towards our environment. Finally, edible electronic components and circuits have potential applications in the biomedical field, including biosensors which can detect variation of different parameters from our oral cavity to the gastrointestinal tract. The biocompatibility of presented materials and components renders them suitable for fabricating sensors or monitoring devices that can be safely ingested and subsequently excreted from the body, thereby minimizing the necessity for invasive procedures. The proposed components that utilize food ingredients to build functional sensors, can be consumed orally and stay inside the mouth monitoring variation in oral microbiome.

As the additional support for the above given proof of the concept, we fabricated sensors with smaller dimensions, as shown in Figure 9a, while the results of electrical characterization are shown in Figure 9b–e.

Finally, artificial saliva was applied to the surface of the sensors with smaller dimensions. Measurements were taken 5 min after applying 0.1 ml of artificial saliva. As the dielectric constant of saliva is higher than the dielectric constant of the test sample itself when it is dry, the application of the artificial saliva resulted in an increase in the capacitance of the interdigital capacitors, as shown in Figure 10.

4. Conclusion

In the last few years, many researchers and research groups have shown interest in the field of edible electronics, which has resulted in an increase in the number of published scientific papers. Still many edible electronic components are not completely biocompatible and biodegradable. In this paper, we have shown that completely edible and biodegradable substrates can be made from food residues, on which it is possible to fabricate functional electronic components that are also completely edible in a simple and fast process. The importance of the present work relies on the formulation of the methodology to use food waste as a source material for electronic components that are edible and safe for

(a)

Capacitor on LOG substrate

(b)

(c)

Capacitor on OGAB substrate

(d)

(e)

Figure 9. a) Fabricated capacitors with smaller dimensions; the corresponding plots of c,e) impedance; and d,f) phase angle of capacitors with smaller dimensions.

use in intraoral sensing. Important parameters, such as pH, conductivity and temperature, are of interest to be measured during eating or during daily activities.^[15,29] In addition to that, salt or sweet level of taken food can be important for people with affected primary sense of taste or different taste disorders, which is very common in case of people with confirmed COVID-19.^[30]

The main contributions of this work can be summarized as follows:

- 1) Several different completely edible, biodegradable substrates were made on which interdigital electrodes made of edible gold were placed.
- 2) IC structures made of edible gold were also placed on the edible substrates, and the characterization was carried out by measuring the following parameters: a) impedance; b) phase angle; c) inductance, as well as measurements of the influence of artificial saliva and mouthwash Paradont on the sensitivity and functionality of the interdigital capacitor.

Figure 10. Sensing demonstration of capacitors on a) LOG and b) OGAB substrates.

- 3) it was shown that the proposed structures, which were fabricated on edible substrates produced on dried food residues, could be used to read certain parameters of the oral cavity.
- 4) In the future, the development of food-waste based conductive edible materials which will be used as electrode material (instead of gold) is planned.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

biomedical applications, edible electronics, electronic components, food waste sensors, interdigital capacitive sensors, natural materials, sensor fabrication

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- [1] C. Chauhan, A. Dhir, M. U. Akram, J. Salo, *J. Cleaner Prod.* **2021**, 295, 126438.
- [2] M. Lins, R. Puppini Zandonadi, A. Raposo, V. C. Ginani, *Foods* **2021**, 10, 1175.
- [3] L. Xue, G. Liu, J. Parfitt, X. Liu, E. Van Herpen, Å. Stenmarck, C. O'Connor, K. Östergren, S. Cheng, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2017**, 51, 6618.
- [4] M. Arshadi, T. M. Attard, R. M. Lukasik, M. Brncic, A. M. da Costa Lopes, M. Finell, P. Geladi, L. N. Gerschenson, F. Gogus, M. Herrero, A. J. Hunt, E. Ibáñez, B. Kamm, I. Mateos-Aparicio, A. Matias, N. E. Mavroudis, E. Montoneri, A. R. C. Morais, C. Nilsson, E. H. Papaioannou, A. Richel, P. Rupérez, B. Škrbič, M. Bodroža Solarov, J. Švarc-Gajić, K. W. Waldron, F. J. Yuste-Córdoba, *Green Chem.* **2016**, 18, 6160.
- [5] A. Gurarslan, B. Özdemir, İ. H. Bayat, M. B. Yelten, G. K. Kurt, *J. Eng. Fibers Fabr.* **2019**, 14, 1558925019856222.
- [6] J. Pupeikė, A. Sankauskaitė, S. Varnaitė-Žuravliova, V. Rubežienė, A. Abraitienė, *Polymers* **2023**, 15, 2539.
- [7] A. S. Sharova, F. Melloni, G. Lanzani, C. J. Bettinger, M. Caironi, *Adv. Mater. Technol.* **2021**, 6, 2000757.
- [8] I. K. Ilic, V. Galli, L. Lamanna, P. Cataldi, L. Pasquale, V. F. Annese, A. Athanassiou, M. Caironi, *Adv. Mater.* **2023**, 35, 2211400.
- [9] Y. Wu, D. Ye, Y. Shan, S. He, Z. Su, J. Liang, J. Zheng, Z. Yang, H. Yang, W. Xu, H. Jiang, *Adv. Mater. Technol.* **2020**, 5, 2000100.
- [10] W. Xu, H. Yang, W. Zeng, T. Houghton, X. Wang, R. Murthy, H. Kim, Y. Lin, M. Mignolet, H. Duan, H. Yu, M. Slepian, H. Jiang, *Adv. Mater. Technol.* **2017**, 2, 1700181.
- [11] A. Tyagi, K. Mishra, S. K. Sharma, V. K. Shukla, *J. Mater. Sci.: Mater. Electron.* **2022**, 33, 8920.
- [12] Y. Lian, M. Ni, L. Zhou, R. Chen, W. Yang, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2018**, 24, 18068.
- [13] G. Saravanavel, S. John, G. K. R., G. Wyatt-Moon, A. Flewitt, S. Sambandan, *arXiv* **2022**, 2202.13782.
- [14] C. J. Bettinger, *Hepatobiliary Surg. Nutr.* **2019**, 8, 157.
- [15] G. M. Stojanović, M. Radovanović, S. Kojić, L. Milić, M. Simić, T. Kojić, R. G. Duval, J. Vukmirović, B. Petrović, *Int. J. of Precis. Eng. Manuf.-Green Tech.* **2023**, 11, 221.
- [16] A. S. Sharova, M. Caironi, *Adv. Mater.* **2021**, 33, 2103183.
- [17] M. Gandhi, *Electrochem* **2023**, 4, 411.
- [18] L. Junwei, M. Yunhai, T. Jin, M. Zichao, W. Lidong, Y. Jiangtao, *Int. J. Food Prop.* **2018**, 21, 1395.
- [19] X. Yue, T. Zhang, D. Yang, F. Qiu, Z. Li, *J. Cleaner Prod.* **2018**, 199, 411.
- [20] L. A. September, N. Kheswa, N. S. Seroka, L. Khotseng, *RSC Adv.* **2023**, 13, 1370.

- [21] I. Betlej, K. Rybak, M. Nowacka, A. Antczak, S. Borysiak, B. Krochmal-Marczak, K. Lipska, P. Boruszewski, *Crystals* **2022**, *12*, 1191.
- [22] S. T. Senthilkumar, N. Fu, Y. Liu, Y. Wang, L. Zhou, H. Huang, *Electrochim. Acta* **2016**, *211*, 411.
- [23] H. I. Abdel-Shafy, M. S. M. Mansour, in *Green Metal Nanoparticles*, (Eds: S. Kanchi, S. Ahmed), Wiley, New York **2018**, pp. 321–385.
- [24] PLANMECA Intraoral sensor, <https://www.planmeca.com/imaging/intraoral-imaging/intraoral-sensor/technical-specifications/> (accessed: December 2023).
- [25] DIGISENS Intraoral Dental X-ray Sensor, <https://elexadent.com/product/digisens-intraoral-dental-x-ray-sensor/> (accessed: December 2023).
- [26] Vatech EzSensor HD Intraoral Sensor, <https://medident.com.au/product/vatech-ezsensor-hd-intraoral-sensor-size-1-5/> (accessed: December 2023).
- [27] J. Rivera-Utrilla, M. Sánchez-Polo, V. Gómez-Serrano, P. M. Álvarez, M. C. M. Alvim-Ferraz, J. M. Dias, *J. Hazard. Mater.* **2011**, *187*, 1.
- [28] M. Radovanovic, S. Kojic, D. Vasiljevic, G. Stojanovic, *Process. Appl. Ceram.* **2018**, *12*, 13.
- [29] J. M. Davidson, R. S. T. Linforth, A. J. Taylor, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* **1998**, *46*, 5210.
- [30] Y. Nanjo, T. Okuma, Y. Kuroda, E. Hayakawa, K. Shibayama, T. Akimoto, R. Murashima, K. Kanamori, T. Tsutsumi, Y. Suzuki, Y. Namba, F. Makino, O. Nagashima, S. Sasaki, K. Takahashi, *Intern. Med.* **2022**, *61*, 2127.